

Nut shells as adsorbents of pollutants: perspectives and obstacles

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Abstract

Shells, kernels and other wastes of fruit and nuts have been investigated by researchers as potential adsorbents for a number of pollutants, or as raw materials for the production of activated carbons and bio-chars to serve the same objective. As such, pistachio nut shell for instance was found to remove methylene blue, Remazol Rot RB (C.I. Reactive Red 198), the Acid Violet 17, Remazol Red (C.I. 18221), cyanide etc. from industrial wastewaters; activated carbons formed by Antep pistachio shells were found to remove Uranium(VI) and Lead(II) while their bio-char removed Pb and Cu, from synthetic aqueous solutions. Activated carbons for wastewater treatment could be effectively prepared from both jacaranda fruit and plum kernels in order to remove lead, acid blue 25 and methylene blue. Activated carbon from pecan nutshell absorbs heavy metals (Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+}). Castor seed hull on the other hand is an attractive low cost adsorbent as compared to activated carbon for the removal of Zn^{2+} from aqueous solution. Cashew nut shell can be used to remove heavy metals, the Congo red dye, methylene blue and phenol from aqueous solutions. The husk of mango seed can be used as carbon precursor or as potential adsorbent for the removal of acid dyes (acid blue 80, acid blue 324, acid green 25, acid green 27, acid orange 7, acid orange 8, acid orange 10 and acid red 1). Mango kernels can be used as adsorbents for the removal of methyl parathion. Mango leaf powder can remove methylene blue from aqueous solution while mango stone bio-composite adsorb the crystal violet dye.

In this work, a comprehensive review of the research conducted on the capacity of nut shells, kernels, etc. of fruits and nuts as potential wastewater purifiers is presented. Their availability and the problems expected from scaling-up laboratory processes are discussed.

Keywords: pistachio nutshell, cashew nutshell, pecan nutshell, plum kernels, mango kernels, mango husk

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